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**LASER PATTERNING ON TRANSITION METAL
DICALCOGENIDES THIN FILMS**

Thesis for graduate's degree

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Laser patterning on transition metal dichalcogenides thin films

The motivation of this project is to study and optimize the use of a simple laser-microscope setup for patterning selected transition metal dichalcogenides. Unlike e-beam lithography or nanoimprinting lithography, our laser patterning setup is clean-room free and does not require sample preparation of any kind, enabling easy access, fast and reliable nanostructuration. As a proof of concept of this technique, we devised an application consisting in fabricating a super-absorber in the whole visible. Since transition metal dichalcogenides thin films show low absorption due to thickness limitation, we utilize light trapping techniques for overcoming this limitation. So, finally, using laser ablation as a lithographic tool, we fabricated a photonic nanostructure of a transition metal dichalcogenide thin film, showing a high absorption in the visible range. In Part 1 we introduce the concept of transition metal dichalcogenide and its properties that will be useful for this work. In Part 2 light trapping is introduced, along with the idea behind its use and how this technique will help us achieve a super-absorber. In Part 3 we talk about the techniques used, either for fabrication or for characterization, such as Raman spectroscopy, electronic microscopy, laser ablation, etc. In Part 4 the optimization of the methods and design of the final structure is explained and discussed. Finally, in Part 5 we explain the measurements and results. At the end, we expect obtaining a thin film with high broadband absorption in the visible range.

1 Introduction

1.1 Transition metal dichalcogenides

Transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDC's) are materials that have the form MX_2 , where M is always a transition metal from the groups 4-6 in the periodic table (Ti, Zr, Hf, V, Nb, Mo, W etc) and X is a chalcogenide (S, Se, Te). Like graphene, these materials, whose crystalline (Fig.1.a) structure consists of several stacked layers coupled by weak Van der Waals interaction and strong in-plane covalent bonds, can be thinned or exfoliated (Fig.1.b) up to a single layer (monolayer), forming what is called a 2D material. In this work, we will focus on semiconductors TMDC's (specifically MoS_2 and $MoSe_2$) that, both in bulk and 2D form, have several unique properties and some of them will be discussed below.

Figure 1: (a) 3D scheme of the MX_2 structure. (b) Optical image of a MoS_2 bulk with the laser spot on it. (c) Optical image of a CVD few-layer MoS_2 flake. (d) Photography of a MoS_2 crystal, that can be found in nature.

1.1.1 Optical properties

Optical properties basically inform us how the material will interact with light. These are inherent and unique for each material in nature and dictate phenomena like refraction, diffraction, reflectance, transmission, photoluminescence and absorption. For this work, the most relevant and important optical properties are:

Refractive index: This quantity (n) informs us the magnitude of the speed of light inside a certain material and consequently, how much the path of light is bent (refracted) when passing from one media to other. For example, an electromagnetic wave traveling in vacuum ($n = 1$) has a certain speed c and wavelength λ_0 . However, when it enters a material like glass with $n = 1,5$, its speed becomes $v = \frac{c}{n}$ and its wavelength $\lambda = \frac{\lambda_0}{n}$. Additionally, according to Snell's law ($n_1 \sin \theta_1 = n_2 \sin \theta_2$) the greater the difference between the refractive index of two media, the greater the deviation of light will be when passing through the surface between them. Also, if light travels from a medium with higher n to a medium with lower n , a phenomena called total internal reflection can happen (which will be discussed later in Section 2.2).

When discussing real life materials though, specially dielectrics, it is necessary to account for a more complete description of the refractive index, since not all light that crosses a material's boundary is reflected or transmitted as in simpler models ($1 = R + T$). Instead, light is also absorbed and the conservation of energy must add a new term for absorption: $1 = R + T + A$. Regarding the refractive index, a common approach is to consider it a complex function of the wavelength of the incident wave: $\tilde{n}(\lambda) = n(\lambda) + i\kappa(\lambda)$, where n is the well-known refractive index and κ is called extinction coefficient. The first still has to do with the (phase) velocity of a wave inside the material and the latter gives information about the attenuation of the wave inside the medium, being related to absorption. Depending on the mathematical approach, whether optics of electromagnetism, is convenient to use either the refractive index or the relative permittivity and permeability of the medium ϵ_r and μ_r . Relative permittivity informs how much the electric field between charges is attenuated inside a material in comparison with vacuum, while the relative permeability tells how well a medium magnetizes in response to a magnetic. The mathematical relation between \tilde{n} , ϵ_r and μ_r is the following [1]:

$$\tilde{n} = \sqrt{\epsilon_r \mu_r}$$

since in the present case the materials are non-magnetic, $\mu_r = 1$ and $\tilde{n} = \sqrt{\epsilon_r}$, leading to an also complex relative electrical permittivity function or dielectric function: $\epsilon_r(\lambda) = \epsilon_1 + i\epsilon_2 = (n + i\kappa)^2$, where $\epsilon_1 = n^2 - \kappa^2$, $\epsilon_2 = 2n\kappa$. Concerning the materials used in this work, they have the following characteristics:

Figure 2: n and k for both materials taken from .

Figure 3: Real and complex part of the relative permittivity. [2]

Figure 2 shows the refractive index, n , and extinction coefficient, κ , spectra of monolayer MoS₂ and MoSe₂ thin films. In both cases the refractive index is very high, specially in the visible range, reaching the maximum values of 6,5 and 4,5 for MoS₂ and MoSe₂ respectively. Regarding the extinction coefficient, in MoS₂ we perceive that the bulk material can be considered lossless for wavelengths higher than 700nm, while in MoSe₂ the decay is slower, meaning that the range of wavelength that can be absorbed is broader than in MoS₂, covering all the visible and even near-infrared (up to approximately 900nm).

Figure 3 shows the dielectric functions (ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 the real and imaginary parts, respectively) for monolayers and bulk materials over a spectral range of 1.5-3eV. While the two graphics show an overall similarity, differences in the width of the resonance peaks can be perceived, being wider in bulk materials compared to the monolayers, which was attributed to the additional optical transitions and carrier relaxation channels arising from interlayer coupling. These properties will be more explored in Part 2 while talking about TMDC-metal interfaces and light trapping.

Energy bands and photoluminescence: Photoluminescence (PL) is a process in which light is emitted from a material in its relaxation process after being absorbed from it. In solids or molecules, incoming photons can be absorbed and make an electron rise from the valence band to the conduction band. The effectiveness of the process is related to the energy and momentum of the incoming photons, the shape of the energy bands and the size of the energy gap. We are interested in semiconductor TMDC's, which have energy gaps ranging typically from 1-2eV. This gap is initially indirect in bulks, but changes with the number of layers and becomes direct in the monolayer limit [3].

Figure 4: Example of calculated MoS₂ bands for (a) Bulk, (b) 4 layers, (c) 2 layers and (d) monolayer. [3]

The possibility of this direct gap enables a higher photoluminescence: since the gap is direct, there is no necessity for phonons to be absorbed or created in the process of light absorption, turning the process more effective than in its counterparts with more layers. In indirect gaps, not all phonons will provide the necessary wavevector to enable the absorption of the photon and creation of an electron-hole pair [4]. Figure 5 show a PL measurement carried in our laboratory for a CVD monolayer flake and a fewlayers flake. As expected, the PL for a monolayer is higher due to its direct band gap.

Figure 5: (a) Measurements of MoS₂ photoluminescence. (b) Optical image showing the regions where we measured PL.

2 Light trapping

Despite possessing high values for refractive index and extinction coefficient, thin films of TMDC's, due to their low thickness, have a limitation in how much light they can absorb. However, manipulating the structure of the TMDC, along with coupling it to other materials, like metals, generates a range of phenomena designated as light trapping modes, which will provide an increase in the absorptive properties of our samples. Light trapping consists in the capturing of as many photons as possible from an impinging electromagnetic wave, with the objective of generating electron-hole pairs [5]. When light enters a material, it can reside in a number of different modes and the goal is to generate as many different resonances as possible, increasing the optical path inside the material and consequently increasing the effectiveness of photon absorption. In the following sections, the light trapping modes relevant for this work are discussed and explained, as well as the nanostructuring chosen by us to enable these modes, a two dimensional photonic crystal. Let's now take a look on each one of them.

2.1 Diffraction:

Diffraction can occur when light encounter obstacles, such as apertures or defects. In order to occur, the following relation has to be obeyed (for diffraction in the same medium):

$$m\lambda_0 = nL(\sin\theta_m - \sin\phi) \quad (1)$$

where m is the order of diffraction, λ_0 the wavelength of the incident electromagnetic wave, n is the refraction index of the medium, L the periodicity of the obstacles/defects, ϕ the incidence angle relative to the normal and θ_m the diffraction angle relative to each order m . A diffraction can produce interference patterns due to optical path differences between wave fronts (and thus a phase difference), such as what happens in Bragg diffraction.

Figure 6: (a) Diffraction inside a material with periodic structures. [7] (b) Diffraction in a four-slit setup.[6]

Equation (1) can also be rewritten as:

$$nK_0 \sin \theta_m = nK_0 \sin \phi + \frac{2m\pi}{L} \quad (2)$$

If the wave is impinging normally, we have:

$$nK_0 \sin \theta_m = \frac{2\pi m}{L} \quad (3)$$

Besides telling us the angles for which diffraction occurs, the equations above also give insights about momentum: K_0 is the free space wavevector $K_0 = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0}$ associated with the incoming wave. Before scattering, the parallel wavevector is:

$$K_{||} = nK_0 \sin \phi \quad (4)$$

After scattering, according to (2), the new parallel component of the wavevector can be written as:

$$K_{||} = \frac{2\pi m}{L} + nK_0 \sin \phi \quad (5)$$

Therefore, when interacting with the periodic structure of the medium, the parallel momentum of the wave is enhanced by $\pm \frac{2\pi m}{L}$, implying in a change in momentum, even if its original parallel momentum is zero. It is worth noting that (like electrons or phonons interacting with the crystalline lattice), the periodic structure only exchanges reciprocal lattice vectors $\vec{G} = \frac{2\pi}{L}$, but instead of L being the crystalline lattice parameter, it can be the distance between slits or holes of the grating, meaning that the increase in momentum is only determined by the array periodicity.

This ability to give parallel momentum to light is of considerable interest in light trapping [7] due to the possibility of obtaining guided modes, plasmonic modes and Bloch modes (as will be discussed below).

2.2 Guided modes:

Guided modes are propagating waves that are strictly confined inside a certain material (waveguide) which, in turn, is surrounded by another material with lower refractive index, like in an optical fiber cable. This is possible because according to Snell's law, total internal reflection can occur if the angle of incidence θ_i has a value greater than the critical angle $\theta_c = \arctan\left(\frac{n_{\text{external}}}{n_{\text{internal}}}\right)$.

Figure 7: Above the critical angle, total internal reflection is possible.

Inside a material, guided modes can provide a more effective absorption, since light spends more time inside the medium, creating more electron-hole pairs and generating more photocurrent.

2.3 Photonic crystals and Bloch modes:

A photonic crystal is a periodic nanostructure that affects the motion of photons in a similar way a crystalline lattice affects the motion of electrons. Instead of being made by atoms or molecules, this photonic lattice is made by different macroscopic media with different refractive indexes/dielectric constants, where the periodic potential is replaced by a periodic dielectric function $\varepsilon_r(\mathbf{r})$ and, depending on the spacial distribution of these different dielectric constants, refraction and reflection of light can produce phenomena similar to the electronic case, like bands, gaps and Brillouin zones. It is possible to design photonic crystals with millimeter dimensions for microwave control or with micron dimensions for infrared control, for example, similarly to periodic waveguides.

Bloch modes are a direct consequence of photonic crystals' discrete translational symmetry, meaning they are not invariant under any transformation, but only under fixed steps that are multiple of the lattice parameter L . Consider a photonic crystal with periodicity of size L in the x direction, incident light with different impingement angles will obtain parallel momentum in \vec{x} due to diffraction with the periodic structure. The Maxwell's equation in a dielectric with no charge accumulation nor electric current have the form [8]:

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0 & \nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} &= 0 \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} &= 0 & \nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} &= 0\end{aligned}$$

Where in a simplistic dielectric model, \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} are given by:

$$\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{r}) = \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}) = \mu_0 \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{r})$$

In general, both \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} are complicated functions of space and time, but when in the presence of a periodic dielectric, the fields can be written as a function of a Bloch coefficient, which has the same periodicity as the photonic lattice:

$$\mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{k}_x}(\mathbf{r}) = \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}_x}(\mathbf{x}, z) \cdot e^{ik_x x}$$

as is stated by Bloch's theorem, where the function $u(x, z)$ modulates the wave in the periodicity direction;

$$u_{k_x}(x, z) = u_{k_x}(x + mL, z)$$

with $m = \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3..$ With the correct periodic boundary conditions applied to the Maxwell's equations, it is possible to find $u_{k_{||}}(x, z)$, $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{r})$ and consequently $\omega(\mathbf{k})$, obtaining a dispersion relation that obeys, due to its \mathbf{k} dependence, the periodicity of the reciprocal lattice:

$$\omega(K_x) = \omega\left(K_x + n \frac{2\pi}{L}\right)$$

where $n = \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3..$ After diffraction, for example, the parallel component of the impinging wave can become a Bloch mode if it encounters sufficient periodicity.

2.4 Thin film Fabry-Pérot interference

This kind of interference occurs in the presence of parallel reflecting surfaces, through which incident light can either be transmitted or be reflected. In a case where one has several stacked materials, reflection occurs in upper and lower boundaries between different materials, and because of difference in optical path, there can be interference between reflected waves. For a certain wavelength λ the conditions are:

$$\Delta x_{const} = m\lambda \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta x_{dest} = (2m + 1) \frac{\lambda}{2} \quad (7)$$

where (6) stands for total constructive and (7) for total destructive interference conditions, Δx being the difference in optical path.

Figure 8: Scheme of a structure in which air, a metal and a TMDC are present.

It is worth noting that Δx depends on the refractive indexes of both media, on the thickness of the TMDC film and on the angles of incidences for both surfaces, θ_1 and θ_2 . Because of this, a very common application of Fabry-Pérot interference is quarter-wave coating, where a dielectric of thickness d is positioned between a medium with lower refractive index n_1 (such as air) and medium with higher refractive index n_3 , in a way that light reflected on the interface air-dielectric will obtain a phase of $\Delta\delta_1 = \pi$ and light reflected on the second interface will increase its phase by $\Delta\delta_2 = 2kn_3d + \pi$, corresponding to the phase gained by traveling a distance $2d$ inside the film with refractive index n_3 . The trick is to make the thickness d be equal to $\frac{\lambda}{4}$, so the phase difference between the two waves as they interfere in air will be

$$\Delta\delta_{total} = \Delta\delta_2 - \Delta\delta_1 = \left(2kn_3 \frac{\lambda}{4} + \pi\right) - (\pi) = kn_3 \frac{\lambda}{2} = \frac{2\pi n_3}{\lambda_0} \frac{\lambda_0}{2n_3} = \pi,$$

where λ_0 is the wavelength of the incident wave in air. So, light will interfere destructively in air, meaning that there will be no reflection.

It is also possible to select a metal for the bottom material, like in Figure 8. In this situation, it is necessary to consider complex refractive indexes and complex reflection coefficients but, at the end, the result is the same: quarter-wave dielectric leads total destructive interference outside (in air). The difference is: with a thick metallic substrate there is no transmission, so the absorption is given by $A = 1 - R$. But we have seen that reflection is zero due to the destructive interference, so we would have total absorption. In order to have this absorption in thinner films, a metal with higher penetration depth can be used. In this last scenario, the phase light obtains due to reflection on the dielectric-metal interface will be higher than π , so the thickness d of the material have to be lower than $\frac{\lambda}{4}$.

2.5 Plasmonic modes

Incoming electromagnetic waves can make the huge number of free electrons in a metal to oscillate around the positively charged cores of metal atoms. Such oscillations are quantized and the quanta are called plasmons. It is possible to induce such plasmons in dielectric-metal interfaces who are called SPPs - surface plasmons polaritons. In this specific case, the oscillations, now involving both charge motion around nuclei in the metal and electromagnetic waves in the dielectric, are surface waves that are guided along the interface, similar to the way light can be guided by an optical fiber.

Let's then consider an electromagnetic wave impinging from a dielectric with complex permittivity $\tilde{\epsilon}_2$ into a metal with complex permittivity $\tilde{\epsilon}_3$ with TM polarization (according to Maxwell's equations, there can be no metal/dielectric TE surface modes) as shown in the figure.

Figure 9: (a) Scheme of light impinging from a dielectric to a metal. (b) Representation of electromagnetic waves and charge density waves of SPP propagating at a metal-dielectric interface [9].

Analyzing the continuity of the momentum parallel to the surface, the following condition must be satisfied for the existence of surface modes [9]:

$$k_{||} = k_{m||} = k_{d||}$$

where $k_{||}$ is the module of the wavevector of the surface wave. It is known that the value of $k_{||}$ will depend on the wavenumber of the incident wave and on both of the permittivities, providing the following dispersion relation :

$$k_{||}^2 = \frac{k_0^2 \epsilon_2 \epsilon_3}{\epsilon_2 + \epsilon_3}$$

Now, a metal's real and imaginary parts of the permittivity vary with the frequency of the impinging electromagnetic wave, and this directly affects the behavior of the surface wave mode. In our device, the dielectric is MoSe_2 and our metal is Molybdenum. The dielectric permittivities are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Real part of the permittivity for MoSe₂ and Mo

Comparing the real part of the permittivity of both materials, we can see from the dispersion relation that $-Re(\epsilon_2) < Re(\epsilon_3) < 0$ for 400nm to 500nm. That means (in lossless materials) that in this range, $k_{||}$ will be a pure complex quantity and the associate mode will be non-propagating, referred to as localized surface plasmon polaritons (Localized SPP's). In our case we have losses and they are called pseudo-propagation SPP's, which are very dampened and they are quickly absorbed. For the rest of the spectrum we have $Re(\epsilon_3) < -Re(\epsilon_2) < 0$ and we recover the normal equation for SPP's.

3 Techniques

3.1 Raman spectroscopy

In this work, the most used characterization technique was Raman Spectroscopy. We use the Raman setup both for characterizing the samples and as a laser ablation lithographic tool. So, we use low powers (i.e. 1mW) to characterized the properties of the samples and higher powers (8mW to 30mW) to ablate the sample with the laser and make a designed pattern. Furthermore, we used the material's Raman spectrum to know whether the laser is well focused or not: we turn the laser on (with low power i.e 1mW so we do not damage the sample) and start to collect the Raman spectrum of the sample. While moving the scanning stage up or down in the Z direction (perpendicular to the sample's plane) the peak's intensity changes, because we approximate or distance the sample from the laser focus. The Z for which the intensity of the peak is higher is identified as the laser optical focus, since it is when the laser delivers more power to the sample and, consequently, the Raman scattering is more intense as well.

3.1.1 Physical principles

Raman effect is an interaction between electromagnetic waves and matter, in which a vibrational quantum is excited or annihilated. This technique is based on collisions between incident photons and matter: most of them are elastically scattered, but few (1 in 10^6 to 10^7 photons) suffer inelastic collisions, which means that the energy of these photons will be higher or lower than the energy of the incident ones. The scattering can be described as an excitation of a molecule to a virtual energy state (lower in energy than a real electronic state) and its de-excitation, that takes back the molecule either to its original energy state, or to a real excited state [11,12]. These possibilities are described bellow:

Rayleigh scattering: Elastic collision, so the scattered photon has the same energy as the initial one and the molecule returns to its initial state.

Stokes scattering: The final state is more energetic than the initial one. Consequently, the scattered photon has less energy and frequency than the incident one.

Anti-Stokes scattering: The final state is less energetic than the initial one, so the scattered photon has more energy and frequency than the incident one.

Figure 11: Scheme depicting the three types of Raman scattering

Figure 12: Scheme of a Raman spectrum

This energy shift between incident and scattered photons is equal to the energy of a vibrational quantum of the material/molecule, meaning that materials with specific vibrational modes will have a specific energy shifts and therefore a "Raman fingerprint".

This shift in energy (frequency) is directly proportional to the so called Raman Shift, defined as:

$$\Delta\bar{\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_0} - \frac{1}{\lambda_1} \right)$$

where λ_0 is the incident photon wavelength and λ_1 is the scattered photon wavelength (these are usually written in cm^{-1}).

A plot of the intensity of scattered photons versus the Raman Shift is called a Raman Spectrum (Figure 12).

It is possible to see that the spectrum is symmetric to the Rayleigh scattering peak ($\Delta\bar{\nu} = 0$) and also that the intensity of the Anti-Stokes peaks is always lower than the intensity of Stokes peaks. Boltzmann distribution can help elucidate this phenomenon: for Anti-Stokes scattering to happen, the molecule's initial state must be an excited vibrational state. Considering this vibrational system as an harmonic oscillator, the energy is:

$$E = h\nu\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)$$

The Boltzmann distribution then tells us the portion of molecules N_n that are thermally excited to some specific energy. So the probability for a molecule to be in an excited state is (N is the total number of molecules)

$$N_1 = N \cdot e^{\frac{-h\nu \cdot \frac{3}{2}}{k_b T}}$$

And the probability for a molecule to be in the ground state is:

$$N_0 = N \cdot e^{\frac{-h\nu \cdot \frac{1}{2}}{k_b T}}$$

It is clear that the probability to find a molecule that behaves like an harmonic oscillator in the ground state is much higher, so Stokes scattering is much more common than Anti-Stokes scattering (the number of Stokes-scattered photons is much higher than the number of Anti-Stokes-scattered photons).

3.1.2 Instrumentation

The system available for our project to measure the Raman Spectra is a Witec Alpha300R Confocal Raman Microscope with a 532nm green laser, that passes through one of the three objective lenses (10x, 50x and 100x augmentation) and reaches the sample. The light that returns to the objective (Raman scattered light) is collected with the same objective, reflected by a beamsplitter and focused again before reaching the detector. This detector consists of a multi-mode optical fiber, which directs the beam to one of the two spectrometer available (600 slits/mm or 1800 slits/mm), each one equipped with a CCD camera (Figure 13).

Figure 13: (a) Alpha300R Confocal Microscope. (b) Witec spectrometers used. (c) Scheme of the laser path of the laser beam, from laser source to CCD.

With the aid of a Witec software it is possible to move the sample in X,Y and Z using a scanning stage. The software also makes possible to center the spectrometer in certain wavelengths. This is important because materials usually have vibrational modes represented by very specific peaks in the spectrum. So being able to discard the rest of the spectrum that is irrelevant (like the Rayleigh scattering peak and vibrational modes from other present substances of no interest) and obtain just the relevant part is convenient.

3.2 Laser ablation

Laser ablation is a technique that consists in removing parts of a solid using a laser. It has several applications in photonics, optoelectronics, electrochemical energy storage and biomedical sensors, all enabled through laser processing, including direct patterning, controllable thinning and even doping. Also important is the simplicity of the technique, because it does not require a clean-room environment, it is fast and easy to execute and can be applied to large-scale fabrication. It has already been shown that it is possible to thin a bulk up to a monolayer using laser. Castellanos-Gomez et al. [13] used a tightly focused continuous wave 514 nm laser to thin MoS₂ down to a monolayer. After scanning the focused laser beam on the multilayered sample with an optimized power density and scanning speed, a uniform monolayer region was created.

Additionally, laser-assisted phosphorus doping in ultrathin (monolayer and bilayer) TMDCs, including n-type MoS₂ and p-type WSe₂, was demonstrated [14] using a continuous wave 532 nm laser. This versatile, air-stable, and tunable method was carried out by varying the duration and intensity of a focused laser beam in a phosphine (PH₃) environment to accomplish the site-specific doping. The laser serves two important functions: creation of sulfur vacancies in the TMDC materials and simultaneous dissociation of the dopant molecules. The released dopant molecules are then incorporated into the vacancy sites.

With a large number possibilities and parameters obtained by literature searching, we have chosen this technique to fabricate a photonic crystal containing arrays of holes with the purpose of obtaining light trapping modes and increase the absorption of our TMDC-based structure.

As showed in figure 14, as the focused beam reaches the sample, its energy is absorbed, heating and even melting or evaporating the most outer portion of material, which can be ejected away from the incidence area. Now, inside the sample, the heat is progressively transferred to the surroundings as time passes and can even alter the structure of nearby areas if the laser energy is too high. For thinner samples, we can expect little surface debris accumulated, creation of vertical holes and also a small effect of the heat propagation due to the dimensional limitation, specially in 2D materials. On the other hand, thicker samples are more likely to have more ejected material, heat accumulation and even new compounds can be created by processes enabled by heat, like oxidation.

Using the setup mentioned above in Section 3.1.2 along with the software provided by Witec, we can move the scanning stage of the microscope. A series of handmade programs in Matlab were developed to translate to the Witec programmable commands and make all kind of patterns. It is worth noting that by using this technique, the size of our structures is limited by the Rayleigh criterion:

$$\Delta d = \frac{0.61\lambda}{NA}$$

where Δd is the diameter of the hole, λ is the wavelength of the laser, and NA is the numerical aperture of the objective. In our case λ is 532nm, NA is 0.9, resulting in a diameter $\Delta d \approx 360nm$.

Figure 14: Scheme depicting how a laser beam can alter a material [15].

To achieve a successful ablation, focusing the laser is an essential step, because it guarantees that the power per unit area is maximum and that we obtain the hole given by the Rayleigh criterion. If the laser is out of focus, the energy transferred to the sample will be lower than expected. So first, we select a low power (1mW for example, so we do not damage and heat the sample too much) and choose a spot where we want to pattern. We turn the laser on and with the aid of an oscilloscope, we obtain the Raman spectrum of that spot. Moving the scanning stage in the Z direction increases or decreases the intensity of the Raman peak, depending whether we are approaching or distancing the sample from the laser focus, in a way that the maximum peak intensity will correspond to the laser focus (higher number of photons per unit area, thus more intensity of Raman scattering). Once the focusing process is done, we can change to the desirable work power and start to pattern.

3.3 Scanning electron microscopy

In our studies, we fabricated a large number of small structures in the micrometric and nanometric scale. Because of this, it can be quite hard to differentiate two points or two lines that exceed the Rayleigh resolution limit. When that is the case, the optical microscope is no longer ideal for imaging and measurement and we have to appeal to the electronic microscopy. In this Section, the main physical principles of SEM are introduced and explained.

Figure 15: (a) SEM QUANTA 650FEG setup used in the project. (b) Image of clusters of 50nm diameter gold nanoparticles demonstrating the high spacial resolution of SEM.

3.3.1 Physical and functioning principles

Inside the column structure of SEM, an electron gun generates electrons (usually, a very strong electric field removes electrons from a tungsten sharp tip) and accelerates them up to 30keV [16]. The diameter of this beam is too high to form high resolution images, so it is necessary to make it pass through a series of alignment and focus apparatuses, such as coils and electromagnetic lenses that use electromagnetic fields to shape the beam. At the end, the spot size is reduced from $\sim 50\mu m$ to tenths of nanometers. Right below the gun column, a stage is located where we put the sample. All this internal environment must be in high vacuum, so the electron beam can travel without being scattered by air. The interactions between the sample and the beam can be elastic or inelastic:

Inelastic scattering and secondary electron emission: Inelastic collisions occur when the electrons from the beam (primary electrons, PE) interact with the electrons of the specimen's atoms, transferring energy to them and causing a potential ionization in the atoms of the sample. These electrons are known as secondary electrons (SE). SEs by definition have less than 50 eV. If the vacancy due to the creation of a secondary electron is filled from a higher level orbital, an X-Ray characteristic of that energy transition is produced. Since SE have low energies, they can easily be reincorporated to the sample. For this, only SE that come from the surface-most atoms are able to reach the detectors. So, measuring secondary electrons is a good way to perceive also the topography of the sample.

Elastic scattering and backscattered electrons: Elastic collisions occur when the electron beam interacts with the nucleus of the specimen's atom, resulting in a change in the direction of the PE, due to Coulomb forces, without a significant change in the energy of the beam (< 1 eV). If the elastically scattered electrons are deflected back out of the specimen, the electron is termed a backscattered electron (BSE). BSEs can have an energy range from 50 eV to nearly the incident beam energy (most backscattered electrons retain at least 50% of the incident beam energy). Since the energy of these electrons are dependent of the interaction with atomic nuclei, the higher the atomic number, usually the greater the energy of the BSE. So, BSE detectors are calibrated to form image contrast based on energy of the electrons that reach them, making a good way to differentiate chemical elements.

Figure 16: (a) Scheme of the interior of a SEM. (b) Inelastic collision generating secondary electrons. (c) Elastic collision generating back scattered electrons. [16]

In this work, all images obtained by SEM were made in high vacuum with an acceleration voltage of 3kV and detecting the secondary electron signal.

4 Design, characterization and fabrication

In this part, it is explained how our samples were made, what we did to characterize the available samples, how was the optimization process for the laser ablation technique and, finally, how we designed our final device. We wanted to be able to pattern thin samples and thicker films. For this, our two elements of study have different thickness: the CVD MoS_2 is composed of small, geometric flakes on a SiO_2 substrate. On the other hand, the MoSe_2 sample is 100nm thick, homogeneous and rough film grown on top of a Molybdenum foil and it was used to make our photonic crystal. With this in mind, let's see a general overview of the whole process, and then, move to the complete explanation: first, after obtaining the MoS_2 and MoSe_2 samples, we used Raman to become familiar with the technique, to know the form of the spectra of each material and to characterize them. Then, we started to learn to ablate using laser, a process that includes learning how altering the parameters (laser power, focus and exposure time) influenced the results we wanted. In order to know the quality of the patterns made, optical and electronic microscopy was used. After that, after optimizing the processes, we moved to the final step of designing and fabricating the photonic crystal using the theoretical and practical experience we obtained from previous parts.

4.1 Deposition techniques

4.1.1 Chemical vapor deposition

This is a technique that is usually employed to fabricate large area samples, with well controlled thickness. The method of production varies from material to material. Usually, one uses a substrate (SiO_2 or some metallic foil are common), along with specific substances and a well defined and controlled atmosphere that, in presence of the adequate pressure and temperature, will allow the desired material to grow. In order to fabricate MoS_2 , for example, it is necessary to put powder MoO_3 and Sulfur below the substrate and expose the system to a Nitrogen atmosphere at around 650°C . The result is the reduction of MoO_3 by the Sulfur vapor, giving rise to MoS_2 , that grows on the substrate [17,18].(See figure 17)

Figure 17: Scheme of the common set-up used to grow MoS_2 by CVD. [17]

To fabricate our MoSe_2 sample, a different type of CVD technique was used, called selenization. This consists in evaporating Selenium and making its vapor reach some specific substrate. In our case, a Molybdenum foil was chosen, which was wrapped around a small SLG (soda-glass-lime) plate above a Si/SiO_2 substrate and placed 45cm away from the recipient with Selenium powder, all inside a quartz tube. For about one hour, the powder is exposed to temperatures around 400°C in an Argon atmosphere and evaporates. Then, Hydrogen is inserted in the chamber, where temperatures rise up to 720°C , and the flow of gas pushes the selenium vapor to the Molybdenum foil, allowing the deposition of Se and the Mo foil to selenize and grow a thin film of MoSe_2 on it.

Figure 18: The selenization of the Mo foil took place during the CVD growth of MoSe_2 flakes on top of a SLG.

4.1.2 Mechanical exfoliation

Consists in successively separating a flake's layers using an adhesive tape. When the tape is folded upon the flake and then unfolded again, the flake is divided in two parts. Eventually, after many repetitions of this movement, it is possible to find monolayer. Although the product of exfoliation is usually very pristine, (because when one divides the flake in two, the region that is facing the person has never "seen" the outer world yet, so is likely not contaminated or dirty) it is not possible to control precisely the size of the samples.

Figure 19: A typical graphene exfoliation using a scotch tape.

4.2 Raman characterization

4.2.1 MoS₂

In order to check features of the samples, like composition and homogeneity and to compare thickness between flakes, Raman spectroscopy is a very reliable technique. First, we compared the Raman spectrum of our CVD MoS₂ to an exfoliated bulk flake. Figure 20 shows both spectra, which has basically three peaks: at 383cm⁻¹, 407cm⁻¹ (MoS₂ characteristic peaks) and around 520cm⁻¹ (SiO₂ peak, our substrate). It is possible to conclude with these spectra that our CVD samples, since the peaks are aligned with the exfoliated peak, have indeed high quality. Furthermore, the silicon oxide peak is only visible in the CVD spectrum because due to its lower thickness, some photons are able to pass through it and reach the substrate, something that is much less likely to happen with the thicker MoS₂ bulk. On the other hand, the intensity of thicker layers' spectra is higher, because there is more material with which the photons can interact with, increasing the number of scattered photons.

Figure 20: MoS₂ Raman signature comparison between an exfoliated bulk and a few layer CVD.

Aiming to know if it is possible to reach lower layers by laser thinning, we patterned a small square region on one fewlayers flake and compared its Raman spectrum with a monolayer. The result shows that it is indeed possible to eliminate upper layers with the laser without destroying the whole sample, which is desirable.

Figure 21: Thicker flake (red) thinned up to a monolayer, since the green and blue spectra are nearly identical.

4.2.2 MoSe₂

Regarding the MoSe₂ sample, we want to know if it is homogeneous (Figure 21). Analyzing the spectra obtained, we can see that independent of the region, they are nearly identical, since all the peaks are aligned with the corresponding well-known MoSe₂ Raman peaks. Also for the intensity of the peaks we can conclude that the white spots correspond to zones not so rough and thinner than the rest of the sample.

Figure 22: Raman spectra in four different regions for MoSe₂ sample.

4.3 Optimization of laser ablation

4.3.1 MoS₂

Despite the simplicity of the technique, we still had to optimize the parameters in order to make good patterns. In these initial MoS₂ samples, the laser power only influenced the amount of heat we would transfer to break the bonds and produce the holes, so we do have to take into account neither heat propagation to neighbor areas nor surface debris.

Figure 23: (a) Lines with 2 μ m period. (b) Lines with 1 μ m period. (c) Array of dots with 0,5 μ m period.

We started making a study concerning power and exposure time, where pairs of holes with $\sim 1\mu$ m period were made and each subsequent pair took longer time to be made. We decided to make holes in pairs because we thought it would be easy to see. Additionally, three values of laser power were used: 10mW, 15mW and 20mW. In order to see the result of these study, we had to go to the electronic microscope, where we photographed and measured the holes:

Figure 24: (a) Pairs of holes with different powers and exposure times. (b) Holes with 20mW were measured using SEM measuring tools.

As the power increases, the holes become more deep and well defined. For 10mW they are almost invisible, so it is not enough power to ablate the sample. Surprisingly, very low exposure time with high power are already enough to produce good holes. Finally, as expected, the size of the holes is determined by our objective and wavelength of the laser and the diameter measured is very close to the theoretical value of 360nm.

4.3.2 MoSe₂

As already stated, this was the sample used to make our photonic crystal. We chose MoSe₂ over MoS₂ because the latter lack some characteristics that are necessary: a broader absorption spectrum in the visible region, a metallic substrate to allow features that occur in metal/dielectric interface, such as plasmonic modes, a big area capable to contain the periodic structures and a considerable thickness to allow Fabry-Pérot interference and guided modes. Now, since the material is different, a different characterization process had to take place: due to the higher thickness, we have to consider the depth of focus, meaning that the sizes of the structures can change if we are out of focus. Besides, a thicker sample means more material, which means heat being dissipated more efficiently, so using high powers can heat nearby areas affecting the quality of structures on that area. Also, the same laser power used in MoS₂ might not be enough or it might be too much for MoSe₂.

We started our optimization process fabricating holes with four different values of power and three different exposure times because, as we attested with MoS₂, low times are already enough to make good holes. When the sample was took to SEM, we could see that, differently from MoS₂, the laser power does not only affects the depth of the holes but also its diameter, meaning the heat of higher powers would spread more to neighbor regions and increase the size of the holes. This is noticeable when comparing results for 12mW with 15mW, since the holes made with the lowest power are much smaller and less deep (Figure 25.a).

Additionally, for the same power, more exposure time also implies bigger holes, which is also expected due to more energy being transferred for more time to the sample.

Finally, by letting the laser rest on a point of our film while measuring the Raman spectrum, we could observe the appearance of a peak that corresponds to an oxidation (Figure 25.b). The peak is negligible for times around 5s but start to be relevant for higher times.

Figure 25: (a) A study regarding power and exposure time. (b) Raman spectra of MoSe₂ disposed as time evolution of Mo₂-O peak.

4.4 Architecture of the super-absorber

Now that we confidently know how to make holes and lines in thin and thick samples, it is time to develop our final photonic crystal architecture. As said in Section 2.3, we need a set of periodic structures that will enable diffraction, Bloch and plasmonic modes. Once we intend to use only the laser to pattern our MoSe₂ film, the size of our periodic objects, the holes, will always have around 360nm due to the Rayleigh criterion. So, it is left for us to choose a lattice parameter L , the number and shape of our array. Since we do not want the holes to overlap, L must be bigger than 360nm and, since we want to absorb in the visible, it would be interesting to have L equal to some visible wavelength, because this would cause this specific wavelength to diffract and give us diffraction modes. As a proof of concept, according to [19], we fabricate a 30x30 square array of holes which is already enough to see light trapping phenomena rising.

We then simulated using a commercial software (Lumerical) based on finite difference time domain method (FDTD) a square array of holes with lattice period $L=450\text{nm}$ and diameter $d = 360\text{nm}$ like the following scheme:

Figure 26: Scheme of the array simulated with $L = 450\text{nm}$.

Finally, attempts to make a 30x30 array were made for different laser powers. We started with 18mW, 250ms for each hole and the result was not good because of the heat dissipation problem: since there are 900 holes being made fast, there was no time for the film structure to cool down. So, the heat would accumulate more and more, until oxidation starts to happen and the shape of the array is lost. To avoid this, we lowered the power to 16mW, which was still not enough, but the overall result was improved. With 12mW and 250ms per hole, we still could not see very well the format of the holes. So, we decided that we would use even lower laser powers and also tell the laser shutter to activate, thus blocking the light for 350ms before going to the subsequent position. This way, there would be time for the array region to cool and the bubble-like oxidation would be avoided. For 10mw, 250ms per point, 350ms sleep time we can already see the holes and the periodicity. Finally we found that the results improved for 9mW and 8mW. Below 8mW we cannot achieve laser ablation in this sample.

Figure 27: Arrays made with (a) 18mW (b) 16mW (c) 12mW (d) 10mW (e) 9mW and (f) 8mW.

Finally, to know if we modified composition of the sample in the process, we took the Raman spectra inside and outside of the array (Figure 27.f).

Figure 28: (a) Raman spectra comparison between the photonic crystal and MoSe₂. (b) Optical image from the regions from which the spectra were taken.

According to the spectra, the photonic nanostructuration did not change the MoSe₂ structure since the characteristic peaks are still present and only slight oxidation is perceived around 700cm⁻¹.

5 Results

In this section we analyzed the results of the simulations and of the measured reflectance. The results are plotted as absorption or extinction instead of reflectance.

5.1 Measurements

In order to know whether our devices really had the super-absorptive properties we wish, we took the samples to be characterized on an advanced Fourier-image-spectroscopy (FIS) in a microscope adapted for reflection measurements. The MoSe₂ film over Mo foil was fixed over a regular microscope glass and put on the microscope. It was illuminated with white light from a tungsten-halogen lamp coupled with a 105 μ m multimode optical fiber, which was collimated and focused onto the sample with an objective (40x, NA =0.75) resulting in a 12 μ m spot, a little smaller than our arrays. The whole system is in open atmosphere, without any common oil immersion. The incident light impinges normally on the array and is reflected by the sample in all directions. This setup is capable to collect reflected light for angles $\theta < \arcsin(\frac{NA}{n_{medium}}) = 48^\circ$. Reflected light passes through a set of mirrors that direct it to a 100 μ m optical fiber connected to a spectrometer. Once our film presents a lot of roughness coming from the Mo foil and once this roughness can interfere in our reflectance results, we opted for normalizing the reflectance spectra against the reflectance spectrum of a Mo foil, identical to ours, measured under the same conditions, in order to avoid the effect of the roughness provided by the substrate.

Figure 29: FIS setup used in this work.

Our experimental result is from the array made by 8mW, 250ms exposure time for hole, 350ms sleep time, 450nm lattice parameter and approximately 100nm thickness, due to being the one which presents the highest absorption. We reached around 90% of broadband absorption in the visible and near infrared range, increasing the absorption of our flat MoSe₂ film over Mo foil successfully (Figure 30.a).

Figure 30: (a) Experimental results. (b) FDTD simulation results.

We compare the experimental results with the numerical simulations of FDTD (Fig 30.b). Both results show a similar average absorption and a similar broadband absorption. Slight discrepancies can come from the fact that in the simulation we consider an infinite periodic array and the roughness is not taken into account. The peaks visible in the absorption spectrum, each one of these corresponds to some light trapping modes that appear due to the architecture of the photonic crystal and can be understood by analyzing the numerically calculated electric field inside and outside the structure (Figure 30):

Analyzing the modes from the Figure 31 we can observe that:

- $\lambda = 450nm$ there is diffraction mode because the lattice period has the same length as the wavelength ($L=\lambda$). Here, we have the so called Rayleigh-Wood anomaly, resulting in a surface wave on the interface photonic crystal/air which is absorbed by the TMDC.
- $\lambda = 536nm$ we observe Fabry-Pérot interference inside the thin film.
- $\lambda = 659nm$ corresponds to a plasmonic mode on the air-metal interface, as it is shown for the typical E_z fields on the metal surface.
- $\lambda = 746nm$ corresponds to a guided mode created inside the TMDC.
- $\lambda = 837nm$ resonance is due to plasmonic mode on the TMDC-metal interface.

Figure 31: (a) Wavelength of the corresponding resonance (b) Absolute value of the electric field in XY plane inside of the TMDC. (c) Z component of the electric field in YZ plane; for the three first wavelengths in the middle of the unit cell, and for the rest in the lateral of the unit cell. The polarization of the electric field of the incident wave is in Y direction.

6 Conclusion

Through this work, we accomplished to make a 2D super-absorber photonic crystal over a MoSe₂ thin film. Overall, our results show that it is possible to modify a regular thin film and fabricate a super-absorber photonic crystal through this simple, safe and fast method of laser ablation. In order to avoid surface debris and excessive heat, we need powers around 8mW and sleep times of 350ms. Integrating the experimental results of flat and modified film, we notice an absorption of 88,2% that corresponds of enhancement of the flat reference of 41,5%.

During this study, I received training in PL, Raman and SEM, learning the theory behind each technique and the experimental methods necessary to execute them. I have exfoliated and characterized samples of TMDC, optimized the laser ablation of CVD samples, wrote the Matlab codes necessary to operate the Witec microscope and also took part in all the reflectance measurements. I also analyzed the light trapping processes involving the photonic nanostructure, improving my understanding about optics, photonics and condensed matter.

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